

Web-based Visualisation Service for Copernicus Satellite Measurements and Automatic Measurement Stations at the Institute of Oceanography and Fisheries

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Abstract: Within the framework of the Referral Centre for the Sea, funded by the Croatian Ministry of Environmental Protection and Green Transition, a web-based visualisation service for remote sensing data, mainly from the Copernicus Marine Environment Monitoring Service, is under development. The service includes an automatic download and data ingestion component for loading data into a relational database with spatial objects. The advanced web-based visualisation service is based on the Leaflet JavaScript library for maps and Highcharts for graphs. The relational database is also connected to a Geoserver instance, enabling standard web GIS services such as WMS and WFS. The service is designed with interactivity in mind and also enables time series visualisations and visual timeline navigation. The main purpose of the service is to serve the public and scientists by allowing easy visualisation of environmental data and quick identification of unusual environmental situations. The service will also serve as a valuable tool for fulfilling the EU Marine Strategy Framework Directive (MSFD) and Water Framework Directive (WFD).

Keywords: Web GIS; oceanography; Copernicus; environmental data.

1 Introduction

The advantages of web applications over desktop applications are clear. In the field of spatio-temporal data, including environmental data and measurements, data flows continuously and can be distributed across many sources. Much of this data is shared by multiple users, and data analysis often requires expert collaboration. It is nearly impossible to synchronise all data locally for use with a dedicated desktop client, and such synchronisation can be time-consuming and labour-intensive. Environmental data contains both spatial and temporal components, and we aim to integrate these by providing new and improved methods and tools within the web environment for efficient, high-quality management of environmental measurements distributed in three-dimensional space and time.

Spatio-temporal data visualisation involves the use of web GIS and various graphical representations of data, providing combined views of space and time (Harbola and Coors 2018). Visualisation in a web environment also includes an interface for human-computer interaction, data transfer to the client side, and user interactions. The time required to collect the data and render the scene is also important for a successful web application, it should

be short enough to ensure smooth use (Mackenzie et al. 2017). Relational databases are now standard as data sources for general types of websites, such as content management systems. They are used for spatio-temporal visualisation for the same reason: they allow easy and fast querying and extraction of data subsets based on user queries.

Environmental science with oceanography is essential for understanding the environment and addressing climate change. Measurements, including satellite observations, fieldwork, and research cruises, are very expensive, which places significant responsibility on data management and data visualisations to ensure these measurements provide new knowledge and understanding of natural processes.

2 Materials and methods

The Copernicus Marine Service is the marine component of the European Union's Copernicus Programme. It provides free, open-access, and science-based information on the state of the Ocean at both global and regional scales. This includes data on the physical Ocean (Blue Ocean), sea ice (White Ocean), and Ocean biogeochemistry (Green Ocean). Funded by the European Commission and implemented by Mercator Ocean International, the service supports the implementation of EU policies and International legal Commitments related to Ocean Governance. It also aims to meet the growing demand for reliable Ocean knowledge across society, and to foster sustainable development in the Ocean sectors by providing state-of-the-art Ocean data and forecasts (Copernicus 2026).

All the products available in the Copernicus Marine Data Store (CMDS) are delivered in the standard NetCDF or Zarr formats, which both allow to store multidimensional scientific data.

2.1 Requirements for web-based visualisation service

The main motive for building the visualisation service was ease of use and features tailored to specific users. On the Internet, it is possible to find many different visualisations of Copernicus marine services, mainly in the form of geoportal layer overlays. To gather valuable information and extract knowledge from these datasets, our users have a few major requirements:

- Combined scalar and vector layers,
- Custom dynamic legend and colours showing only values present in the current scene (including zoom levels),
- Possibility to obtain time series for each point,

- Custom time axis for identifying unusual and interesting scenes,
- Integration with in-situ data already present in the environmental database.

Because of these requirements, we chose to implement a web-based visualisation service using a relational database. A relational database allows us to easily generate various statistics. The drawback is that this type of data management requires a relational database. Additionally, loading a significant amount of data requires indexing and optimisation, otherwise, queries to the database will become slow, leading to a poor user experience.

Parameters chosen for our services will mainly be from Blue Ocean, focusing on physics (e.g., temperature, currents, waves), and Green Ocean, which covers ecosystem health (e.g., chlorophyll, nutrients, carbon). These parameters are also present in in-situ measurements and are important for good environmental status.

2.2 Data flow and processing

Files are downloaded from Copernicus Marine Data Store by scheduled bash scripts using wget or Copernicus cli tool for Linux. NetCDF utility ncdump is used to convert files from NetCDF format to CDL (network Common Data form Language) (NetCDF Users Guide 2026). Finally they are loaded to database and processed.

In our case, we use Oracle Database Standard Edition on the Enterprise Linux platform. There are four groups of tables for each parameter (Figure 1):

- Tables to store spatial locations for different model grids,
- A table to store header data for each scene: date and time of the scene, loading time, and parameter averages, minimums, and maximums,
- A table to store raw data for each scene,
- Tables to store processed data for each parameter for visualisation purposes: spatial averaging, grouping, and indexing of values.

3 Results

Our web-based visualisation service is available as a web application or web page (Figure 2, Izor 2026). It is a responsive web application and can be used on mobile devices with small screens.

Figure 2. Web application main screen.

Figure 1. Table schema.

3.1 Data visualization

All data visualisation is client-based. The server delivers the data required for visualisation, which is then rendered in the user's browser. This approach allows for better interactivity, as it is easy to identify individual visualisation elements, such as a point on a map or a specific value in a graphical view. For basic spatial visualisation, we use the Leaflet API, which is based on JavaScript and AJAX calls to retrieve data in JSON format. For the entire model area, averaged fields with a fixed range are displayed. The user can zoom in and load the native model resolution with a customised range for that area. Scalar fields represent numerical parameters (e.g. sea temperature or salinity), while vector fields represent vector values (e.g. sea currents or wind). Both types of fields can be switched on or off. A vector field can be combined with one of the scalar fields. For the vector field, each vector is positioned at a grid point (centred). Data for field visualisation is loaded separately from the main page, asynchronously in the background.

3.2 Web application performance

One of the main challenges during the development of the Copernicus web application was ensuring that the web page loaded within a reasonable time. The primary issue is that, in addition to the time required by the browser to draw and render the entire web page, each page element (such as the display of a model field) requires about 1 MB of data to be loaded. The web page is designed to initially load only the map, without parameter visualisation. The user can then choose scalar and vector parameters to load. Each step (initial load, scalar parameter load, and vector parameter load) typically takes under or approximately one second on both desktop and mobile browsers (tested on average wireless and mobile networks). This amount of time is acceptable for smooth use.

3.3 Dynamic legend and colours

The ranges of displayed sizes must be adjusted according to the user's selected area. For example, if 20 different

colours are used for the display and the range, such as sea temperature, is 10 °C for the entire model area, then one colour represents a range of 0.5 °C. If the user zooms in on an area where the temperature oscillation is 4 °C, the display resolution becomes 0.2 °C, making it possible to observe finer changes in the values of the displayed parameter for the selected area (Figure 3).

4 Discussion

Our web-based visualisation service is still in development. In building this service, we are focused on our users' needs. Our users include scientists, decision-makers, and the general public. This service is one of the components in the information system for the Sea, created to fulfil tasks of environmental protection according to national and EU legislation. Already completed components are the Cruise summary report database, the monitoring database for in situ measurements, and the Indicator database (Ivanković et al. 2019). These components form an information chain from metadata about cruises, to raw measured data, to aggregated data for indicators. Satellite data, modelled data, and data produced by various AI models are the next important components in the information services for monitoring sea state. The technology and methods chosen for our web-based services have been selected to meet future needs for close integration with other existing services. Our approach is not the usual one for this task, but we prefer to adjust technology for specific targets and user requests rather than tailor solutions according to available technology and the most straightforward approach.

5 Conclusions

To better understand the environment, various measurement systems and models are being developed, producing gridded value fields. Effective interpretation of this information requires good visualisation. Our solution is based on dynamically created scenes on the client side using JavaScript. This type of visualisation enables integration with other data from the database and provides

Figure 3. Adaptive range and colours for same area and scene.

interactivity. Using a relational database within model visualisation is not common practice and requires optimisation for smooth operation. Managing large amounts of data within the database is challenging, but feasible. Further development of the described visualisation will include other available data sources for targeted areas, as well as graphical representations of parameter changes over time for any selected point in space (the nearest grid point). Additionally, during the model run, results can be compared not only with data from the automatic measurement system, but also with all available oceanographic and meteorological data. Furthermore, the data will be used for machine learning procedures and the prediction of values for additional parameters.

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